

2EN Enallaktiki Energiaki

renewable energy services and applications

Lidar in Wind Energy: Industry Perspectives, Challenges and Opportunities

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2EN S.A.
Amfiklia 35002, Greece
www.2en.com

2EN Company

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- **Leading Greek company specializing in wind potential measurements and assessment since 2000.**
- **Accredited under EN ISO 17025 for high-precision wind data measurements.**
- **Extensive experience with 1000+ meteorological mast installations and advanced LiDAR measurement systems.**
- **Provides end-to-end services: station installation, LiDAR deployments, maintenance, data collection and reporting.**

2EN Activities - Vertical Lidars

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- Installations across diverse onshore terrains
- Certified measurements (by Hellenic Accreditation System)
- Reliable data for wind resource assessment

2EN Activities - Scanning Lidars

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- Offshore wind measurement campaigns with Single and Dual Scanning Lidar systems.
- Projects in Greece and Azerbaijan.
- Validation of DSL Wind Measurements against Met Mast Data in Greece: Strong Correlation observed at both 100 m and 200 m Range Gate Lengths.

Full Results coming soon

Meeting industry needs with Lidar

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- **Continuous, high-quality, and validated data across all conditions**
- **Reliable uncertainty quantification for bankable projects**
- **Harmonized international standards and certification**
- **Seamless integration with industry workflows and software tools**
- **Cost-effective solutions for large-scale adoption**

Key challenges

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Vertical Profiler Lidars

Performance in complex terrain

Extreme Weather Conditions (Fog / Rain)

Scanning Lidars

Stability of SL system

Turbulence Intensity (TI) measurements

International Standard

Future Outlook

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- **Advances in scanning lidar:**
wind field reconstruction in complex terrain & offshore
- **Improved scanning lidar accuracy & certification:**
building trust and comparability
- **AI/ML & automated Quality Control:**
real-time data validation and advanced forecasting
- **Integrated networks:**
lidars + masts + satellites + models
- **Collaboration drives progress:**
industry, academia & certification bodies
- **Lidar → essential tool:**
from a promising technology to the backbone of wind energy

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Thank you!

Any Questions (?)

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